

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON DURABILITY PERFORMANCE OF ENGINEERED BAMBOO UNDER DRY-WET AND THERMAL COUPLED CYCLES

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ABSTRACT

In order to investigate the effects of temperature and humidity change on the properties of engineered bamboo, artificial accelerated aging tests were conducted under dry-wet and thermal coupled cycles. The physical and mechanical properties of glued laminated bamboo, bamboo scrimber and reference Douglas fir specimens after accelerated aging under dry-wet and thermal coupled cycles were tested. Results show that the flexural properties of engineered bamboo are more sensitive to the change of environmental temperature and humidity. When used in conditions with obvious temperature and humidity changes, protection is required to maintain the stability of moisture content.

KEYWORDS

glued laminated bamboo; bamboo scrimber; durability; dry-wet and thermal cycling; physical and mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Bamboo is a renewable and biodegradable material with low carbon footprint (van der Lugt et al. 2006; Issa and Kmeid 2006). Glued laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber are two important types of engineered bamboo that can be used as structural material. Glued laminated bamboo is fabricated by cutting strips (lamina) from round bamboo stem, drying these to moisture content of 8%~12%, and assembling and gluing them into rectangular cross sections (Mahdavi et al. 2010; Sharma et al. 2015). Bamboo scrimber, also known as parallel strand bamboo, is fabricated by cutting bamboo into strips, drying and gluing them parallel to each other, typically in a mould under pressure (Zhou et al. 2012; Li et al. 2013). Through standardized processing, engineered bamboo has better mechanical properties than round bamboo and some wood products.

The durability of engineered bamboo has a significant impact on the safety performance of engineered bamboo structures. The cellulose, lignin and other biomass components in bamboo are sensitive to the change of natural environment (Jayanetti and Follet 1998). Climate change is the result of multiple factors. The change of environmental temperature and humidity is among the most important factors affecting the durability of biomass materials. In order to investigate the effects of temperature and humidity change on the properties of engineered bamboo, artificial accelerated aging tests were conducted under dry-wet and thermal coupled cycles. The physical and mechanical properties of

glued laminated bamboo, bamboo scrimber and reference Douglas fir after accelerated aging under dry-wet and thermal cycles were tested to evaluate the anti-aging performance of engineered bamboo under natural factors.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

The parameters commonly used in structural design: bending strength, modulus of elasticity in static bending, strength and modulus of elasticity in compression parallel to grain, as well as the physical properties including dimension, mass and density, were selected to evaluate the anti-aging performance of engineered bamboo and reference Douglas fir specimens. There was no standard test method for engineered bamboo products currently, so the test standards for timber in China were adopted. The test parameters and corresponding test standards are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Test parameters

Test parameter	Dimension of the specimens	Test standard
Dimension, mass and density	20mm×20mm×20mm	GB/T 1933-2009
Bending strength	20mm×20mm×300mm	GB/T 1936.1-2009
Modulus of elasticity in static bending	20mm×20mm×300mm	GB/T 1936.2-2009
Strength in compression parallel to grain	20mm×20mm×30mm	GB/T 1935-2009
Modulus of elasticity in compression parallel to grain	20mm×20mm×60mm	GB/T 15777-2017

The accelerated aging treatment referred to the test method in GB/T 17657-2013. The steps of aging treatment are as follows.

1) A dry-wet cycle was conducted first: the specimens were soaked in clear water at a temperature of $(20\pm 3)^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 hours; then after wiping dry the surface, the specimens were put in the electric blast drying oven, at a temperature of 60°C for 4 hours, and $(103\pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$ for 8 hours.

2) Followed by 4 thermal cycles, each cycle included the following steps: the specimens were put in the electric blast drying oven at a temperature of $(80\pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$ for (120 ± 10) minutes, and then in a refrigerator at a temperature of $(-20\pm 3)^\circ\text{C}$ for (120 ± 10) minutes. One dry-wet cycle and four thermal cycles are regarded as a coupled cycle.

There were 3 group of specimens, and each group included 6 specimens for each parameter. Two and eight coupled cycles were conducted respectively, and one group was placed in a standard curing box with a constant temperature of $(20\pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$ and humidity of $(65\pm 5)\%$. After coupled cycling, the specimens were cured in the above standard curing box until reaching equilibrium moisture content before mechanical testing.

TEST RESULTS

Physical properties

After eight coupled cycles, the color of the three materials all turned dark and black, as shown in Fig. 1. Cracks in parallel-to-grain direction appeared on the surface of glued laminated bamboo, and

cracks in perpendicular-to-grain direction appeared on the surface of Douglas fir. There were no obvious cracks on the surface of bamboo scrimber.

The average rate of change of dimension in three directions, mass and density after two and eight cycles are shown in Table 2, in which positive values indicate an increase and negative values indicate a decrease. L_1 and L_2 are in the perpendicular-to-grain direction, and L_3 is in the parallel-to-grain direction. In glued laminated bamboo, L_2 represents the pressing direction of bamboo strips. And for the other two materials, there is no difference between L_1 and L_2 .

Table 2 Rate of change of physical properties (%)

Material	Parameter		Rate of change	
			2 cycles	8 cycles
Glued laminated bamboo	Dimension	L_1	-0.63	-1.40
		L_2	-0.45	-0.61
		L_3	-0.17	-0.33
	Mass		-1.82	-1.76
	Density		-0.60	-0.30
Bamboo scrimber	Dimension	L_1	-0.13	-2.06
		L_2	-0.65	-2.15
		L_3	-0.10	-0.22
	Mass		-3.10	-5.48
	Density		-3.42	-1.14
Douglas fir	Dimension	L_1	-0.58	-1.64
		L_2	-0.81	-1.20
		L_3	-0.29	-0.37
	Mass		-2.98	-3.51
	Density		-0.94	-0.68

The dimension of the three materials all decreased in three directions after coupled cycling, and generally the decrease in the perpendicular-to-grain direction was greater than that in the parallel-to-grain direction. In the perpendicular-to-grain direction, the order of dimensional change rate was: bamboo scrimber > Douglas fir > glued laminated bamboo; and in the parallel-to-grain direction, the order was: Douglas fir > glued laminated bamboo > bamboo scrimber.

The mass and density of the three materials all decreased with the increase of the aging cycles. The mass and density of bamboo scrimber decreased the most, due to its largest glue proportion, followed by Douglas fir. Generally, the dimension and mass of glued laminated bamboo were less affected by the changes of temperature and humidity.

Mechanical properties

The change of bending strength with the increase of coupled cycles of the three materials is shown in Fig. 2. After coupled cycling, the bending strength of the three materials all decreased. After eight coupled cycles, the bending strength of glued laminated bamboo, bamboo scrimber and Douglas fir decreased by 39.6%, 9.7% and 5.5% respectively, among which glued laminated bamboo showed the largest decrease.

Fig. 2 Variation of bending strength

The change of modulus of elasticity in static bending with the increase of coupled cycles of the three materials is shown in Fig. 3. The modulus of elasticity in static bending of bamboo scrimber and Douglas fir increased with the increase of coupled cycles, which increased by 29.1% and 29.7% respectively after eight coupled cycles. The modulus of glued laminated bamboo decreased first by 15.6% after two coupled cycles, and then increased by 2.8% after eight coupled cycles, compared with the initial modulus.

Fig. 3 Variation of modulus of elasticity in static bending

The change of strength in compression parallel to grain with the increase of coupled cycles of the three materials is shown in Fig. 4. The compression strength of bamboo scrimber and Douglas fir increased with the increase of coupled cycles, which increased by 80.5% and 23.0% respectively after eight coupled cycles. After dry-wet and thermal cycling, failure of bamboo scrimber specimens was more brittle accompanied by a loud crack, due to hardening of the glue. On the other hand, the compression strength of glued laminated bamboo decreased first by 27.5% after two coupled cycles, and then increased but still lower than the initial strength.

Fig. 4 Variation of strength in compression parallel to grain

The change of modulus of elasticity in compression parallel to grain with the increase of coupled cycles of the three materials is shown in Fig. 5. The modulus of glued laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber decreased first by 7.4% and 4.1% respectively after two coupled cycles, and then increased by 9.0% and 11.4% respectively after eight coupled cycles, compared with the initial modulus. The modulus of Douglas fir increased first by 20.9% after two coupled cycles, and then decreased slightly after eight coupled cycles, with an increase of 17.6% compared with the initial modulus.

Fig. 5 Variation of modulus of elasticity in compression parallel to grain

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the physical and mechanical properties of glued laminated bamboo, bamboo scrimber and reference Douglas fir specimens after accelerated aging under dry-wet and thermal coupled cycles were tested. The effects of humidity and temperature change on the properties of bamboo and timber were investigated.

After dry-wet and thermal cycling, the dimension of the three materials all decreased in three directions, and the decrease in the perpendicular-to-grain direction was greater than that in the parallel-to-grain direction. The mass and density of the three materials all decreased, among which bamboo scrimber decreased the most, due to its largest glue proportion. The dimension and mass of glued laminated bamboo were less affected by the changes of temperature and humidity.

In terms of bending properties, the bending strength of the three materials all decreased, and glued laminated bamboo showed the largest decline. The modulus of elasticity in static bending of bamboo scrimber and Douglas fir increased after accelerated aging, while glued laminated bamboo showed some decrease followed by an increase trend.

In terms of compression properties, the strength in compression parallel to grain of bamboo scrimber and Douglas fir increased after accelerated aging, while glued laminated bamboo showed slight decrease. The modulus of elasticity in compression parallel to grain of the three materials all increased after accelerated aging.

In general, the flexural properties of engineered bamboo are more sensitive to the change of environmental temperature and humidity. When used in conditions with obvious temperature and humidity changes, protection is required to maintain the stability of moisture content.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Each paper shall include one of the following data availability statements. Statement 3 is most commonly used:

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.